

Short name	Compensation for leakages	Long name	Penalties for leakages and other disturbances in national legislation
Geographical scope	National + International		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Does national legislation – or do the permitting provisions – foresee compensation requirements imposed on the operator in case of leakage and other disturbances in CCUS value chains – which actor is to be penalised if leakage and other disturbances happen (capture, transport, storage provider)?</p> <p>Carbon market standard setters have developed instruments to regulate any financial harm arising from leakage (e.g. Verra’s non-permanence risk tool for geological storage). National regulators arguably need to have regulations or permitting-provisions in place in order to impose penalties on private operators of CO2 transport and storage sites.</p> <p>The EU CCS Directive provides for some such guidance, but national legislation needs to operationalize them.</p> <p>Some uncertainty also pertains to the liability distribution amongst carbon market standard setters, project proponents and national governments.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What about leakage happening in shared, cross-border infrastructure? • What about various entities operating along the CCS value chain? • What about leakage happening during CO2 transport via ships, who are in international waters? 		
Other issues this affects	MRV - who is responsible for reporting leakage?		
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vinca, A.; Emmerling, J.; Tavoni, M. (2018): Bearing the Cost of Stored Carbon Leakage 		